

Survey and Documentation of Ethno Medicinal practices in vogue, for curing different ailments in Munchingi puttu Mandal of Eastern Ghats of Andhra Pradesh, India

Vidyadhara Jayanth Babu Nagireddy ¹ and Setu Madhava Rao Devakoti ^{2,*}

¹ District Forest Officer (Retd.) Dept. of Forestry, Andhra Pradesh, India.

² Lecturer in Botany, Government Degree College, Gajapathinagaram, Vizianagaram (Dt), Andhra Pradesh, India.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 24(02), 1082–1091

Publication history: Received on 25 September 2024; revised on 04 November 2024; accepted on 06 November 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.24.2.3380>

Abstract

Present communication deals with the Ethno Medicinal Practices for Treating of different ailments of mankind. The present study comprises of a total of 47 no. of ethno-medicinal formulae, provide information in detailed on the therapeutic values of 49 plant species belonging to 45 genera and 30 families, covering 18 numbers of different ailments. Information on botanical details and method of preparation, administration of medicines is presented. This data would aid as baseline information for investigators working on ethno botany and ethno medicine.

Keywords: Ethno Medicinal Formulations; Plant Species; Some Ailments; Dosages; Munchingi Puttu Mandal; Eastern Ghats of India.

1. Introduction

Ethnomedicine plays a vital role in rural India even though a lot of advancement reported in modern medical system [1]. In modern era it is necessary to documentation and evaluate this information for its commercial use as ethno medicinal treatments of plants is an important criteria used by the pharmaceutical industry in searching new therapeutic agents [2]. Murty and Narasimha Rao (2010) studied the unique ethno medicinal properties of some plant species of Andhra Pradesh [18]. Narasimha Rao and Murty (2014) documented some important medicinal applications of Mangrove plant species of Andhra Pradesh [6]. Jayanth Babu et al., (2017 and 2018) presented the data on application of ethno medicinal plants to treat bone fractures [7,8]. Narasimha Rao (2020) studied the flora of Mangrove Species utilized for ethno medicinal practices in Gautami Godavari Estuary, AP. [14]. Jayanth Babu et al. (2020A; 2020B; 2020C; 2020D and 2020E) studied the plant species used for the treatment of arthritis, sports injuries, osteo arthritis and other ailments of human beings [9,10,11,12,13]. Jayanth Babu and Narasimha Rao (2021) explored the ethno medicinal practices of *Aeglemarmelos* in Eastern Ghats of India [15]. Jayanti Babu et al. (2024 A) studied ethino medicinal plant treatment practices in Vogue for curing different ailments in the villages of Alluri Sithararaju District, the Eastern Ghats of Andhra Pradesh, India [17]. In the present investigation data was collected on the usage of some medicinal plants to treat various ailments of mankind in different villages of Munchingi Puttu Mandal of Eastern Ghats of A.P., India.

1.1. Study sites

The Eastern Ghats of India are a long chain of broken hills that pass mainly through five states namely Odisha, Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu. This run about 1700 km (1100 miles) with a width varies from 100 to 200 kms in between Mahanadi River in the North to the Vaigai River in the South, along the East Coast of India. Munchingi Puttu Mandal lies in between latitudes 18°21'25.200" N and longitudes 82° 30' 54.000" E. The type of vegetation varies from scrub jungles and dry deciduous to moist deciduous forests. Tribes like Koyas, Kondareddis,

* Corresponding author: Setu Madhava Rao Devakoti

Valmiki, Chenchu, Lambada, Jatapu, Savara, Bagata, Porja, Khonds, are the inhabitants of the forest regions of Eastern Ghats of Andhra Pradesh region. In the present study data collected from the tribal or herbal doctors and local aged people residing in Munching Puttu Mandal, of A.P. India.

2. Materials and methods

Information on medicinal formulae and relevant details for treating various diseases was obtained through interacting with tribal doctors as well as native healers and village heads. The data thus obtained was cross verified and ascertained in the field with the local doctors and tribal people in that region. The methodology was followed as described by Jain (1999), Hemadri (1994), Martin (1995) and Jayanth Babu et al (2017 and 2018) [3,4,5,7&8]. Procedures for preparation of infusions, dosages and poultices used for curing different ailments followed by Jayanth Babu et al (2024) [16].

3. Results and discussion

This investigation comprises of a total number of 47 formulae, 49 plant species belonging to 45 genera and 30 families have been identified as potential source for treating about 18 no. of different type of ailments or health exigencies.

The scientific names of the species along with families, vernacular names, plant part(s) used, doses and mode of preparation are recorded as detailed below.

Table 1 Ingredients, Formulae preparation Methods and Usages.

Sl. No. of the species	Name of the Plant Species; Family; Local Name; Common name.	Name of the health exigency; ailment or disease.	Plant parts used; Dose; Method of preparation / Formulae and usage. (F1 to F 57 indicated herein are the formulae)
1) 2)	<i>Calotropisprocera</i> ; Apocynaceae; Jilledu; Apple of Sodom; Giant milk weed plant; <i>Trachyspermum ammi</i> ; Apioaceae;. Ajowan; Vaammu;	For curing Asthma	F1*1) Buds of tender leaves of <i>Calotropis</i> 10 gr. taken, + 2) <i>T.ammi</i> 5 gr seeds are taken, individually made into a fine powders. 1 and 2 are made into a fine paste by adding jaggery 10 gr, and by using adequate water - made into pills of each weighing 500 mg. and given @ 1 pill per 1 day, early in the morning in empty stomach with water for 15 to 20 days.
3)	<i>Strichnosnux - vomica</i> ; Loganiaceae; Musti; 3* <i>Strichnosnux- vomica</i> . Loganiaceae; Musti; 3* <i>Strichnosnux - vomica</i> ; Loganiaceae; Musti;	For curing Asthma For curing Asthma. FOR CURING, *Back pain, *Rheumatoid arthritis, * Joints pains, *Purification of Blood and *Asthma. This formula is the answer for	F2* Nux- vomica seeds 10 gr are soaked in water for 3 days and then inserted in to fresh cow dung for 4 more days. On 7 th day, all the seeds are removed from cow dung and washed them. Removed seed coats and the dormant embryo portions and discarded. Afterwards, dried well under sun, fried in an earthen or iron or stain less steel pan, till seeds color becomes brown. Afterwards, finely powdered screened using a thin white cloth and preserved in an air tight glass bottle. Given twice in a day along with hot water @ 100 mg of this powder per each dose along with 1 gr. of tri-phala powder for 40 days . F3* Stem bark of <i>Strichnos</i> is grinded finely and mixed well in 60 ml of Luke warm water and given to Asthma patients @ 3 ml per each time, twice /day for a period of 10 days. F4* Nux- vomica seeds 15 gr are soaked in water for 3 days and the soaked seeds are inserted completely in to fresh cow dung for 4 more days. Removed the seeds from the cow dung; washed them. Removed seed coats and dormant embryos

	<p>3*<i>Strychnosnux-vomica</i>; Loganiaceae; Musti;</p>	<p>Rheumatoid arthritis and severe Back pain. For curing Bronchitis</p>	<p>and discorded. The Cotyledons mixed with 10 gr of black peppers are finely grinded in a mortar for 2 days using adequate quantity of pure juice extracted from ginger rhizomes. Afterwards grinded for 2 days or 48 hours in a mortar using adequate quantity of drumstick leaves juice. Made into 100 mg /pill. Dried and stored in a clean air tight bottle. Given twice /day @ 1pill with 1 gr of triphala powder and water for 40 days. F5*<i>Nux - vomica</i> stem bark is rubbed on a grinding stone to get a fine paste and 500 mg of this paste is given orally for smearing on tongue, once in a day for a period 10 days.</p>
4)	<p><i>Datura stramonium</i>; Solanaceae; Nallavummetha. 1*<i>Calotropisprocera</i>; Apocynaceae; Jilledu;</p>	<p>For curing Asthma and related fevers</p>	<p>F6*Flowers of <i>Datura</i> 10 gr; and seeds of <i>Calotropis</i> 10 gr; Rock salt 5 gr; Black pepper seed 5 gr are grinded in a mortar using pure juice obtained from ginger for 3 hours. Made in to pills of size each 200 mg and given in the morning in empty stomach with water for 40 days for curing Asthma.</p>
5)	<p><i>Cissus quadrangularis</i>; Vitaceae; Nalleru <i>Argemone mexicana</i>;</p>	<p>For curing Asthma</p>	<p>F7* <i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> clean tender stems paste 50 gr and <i>Argemone</i> root bark-- paste 50 gr and Common salt 50 gr are mixed together and grinded well to get a fine paste, made into pills of each 1 gr; Dried well and stored. These pills are given to Asthma patient to consume orally @ 1 pill in the morning and 1 in evening for 40 days for curing Asthma.</p>
6)	<p>Papaveraceae; Balurakkasi; Mexican Popppy</p>		
7)	<p><i>Achyranthes aspera</i>; Amaranthaceae; Vuttareni; Apamarga.</p>	<p>For curing ASTHMA</p>	<p>F8* <i>Achyranthes</i> seeds 5 gr - fine powder and <i>Pepper</i> seeds 10 gr fine powder are mixed in <i>Acacia</i> gum in adequate quantity; made into pills of each 500 mg to 1 gram. Given twice or thrice in a day with warm water for 15 days.</p>
8)	<p><i>Vachellia nilotica</i>; Fabaceae; Nallathumma; Babul;</p>		
9)	<p><i>Adathoda vasica</i> / <i>Justica adathoda</i>; Acanthaceae; Vasaka Addasaram; Malabar Nut.</p>	<p>FORCURING ASTHMA</p>	<p>F9* Fresh <i>Adathoda</i> plants along with leaves, flowers, fruits stem and roots about 10 kgs of are collected, dried well and burnt to ashes. This ash is mixed in an earthen tub or vessel containing 20 lits. of fresh water, stirred well once in 4 hours with a stick for 3 days. Floated materials of the plants available on the top layer of the water are removed carefully. After stirring well again, this water is transferred in to a big vessel or Kadai or Iron bhandi kept on fire and boiled till all this 20 lits. of solution is evaporated leaving at the bottom the salt or extract of <i>Adathoda</i>; which is collected carefully in a dry condition and preserved in an air tight glass bottle. 50 to 100 mg of this salt or extract is mixed in 1gram of triphala powder (Sl. Nos 10, 11 and 12) and given to asthma patients, to be taken orally with Luke warm water in the morning and repeated in evening for 40 days.</p>
10)	<p><i>Terminalia bellerica</i>; Combretaceae; Taani</p>		
11)	<p><i>Terminalia chebula</i>; Combretaceae; Karak;</p>		
12)	<p><i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>; Euphorbiaceae; Amla; Usiri.</p>		

<p>13)</p> <p>14)</p>	<p>9 *<i>Adathoda vasica</i> / <i>Justica adathoda</i>; Acanthaceae; Vasaka Addasaram; Malabar nut.</p> <p>9*<i>Adathoda vasica</i>.</p> <p>9*<i>Adathoda vasica</i>.</p> <p><i>Solanum surattense</i>; Solanaceae; Vaakudu; Kantakari;</p> <p>14) <i>Nicotina tabacum</i>; Solanaceae. Tobaco; Pogaku; 7*<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>; Amaranthaceae; Vuttareni; Apamarga.</p>	<p>FOR CURING ASTHMA</p> <p>For curing T.B.</p> <p>For curing Asthma</p>	<p>F10* Every day in the morning, one Omelet is prepared (using a duck egg) by mixing 15ml of pure juice of <i>Adathoda</i> leaves, 1 gr of black pepper powder and a pinch of rock salt and given to Asthma patient to consume orally every day up to 3 weeks.</p> <p>F11*1 kg root bark of the <i>Tamarind</i> trees burnt to ashes and the essence or the salt is extracted as referred and described in formula no 9. 100 mg of this salt or extract is mixed in the 5 ml of the leaves juice of <i>Adathoda</i> along with 1 gr of pepper powder and administered orally early in the morning, every day, for 40 days.</p> <p>F12*Whole plants of these species, <i>Adathoda</i>, <i>Solanum surattense</i>, <i>Nicotina</i>, <i>Achyranthes</i> along with flowers, fruits, leaves, stem, and roots are collected @ each 2 kgs per each species, from their natural habitat, under hygienic condition, cleaned properly, dried well, burnt to ashes for preparing the extract or salt or essence done as referred above against F9 of this paper. Given to the patients @ 50 mg / dose mixed with 2 ml of honey in the morning and evening and for 40 days.</p>
<p>15)</p> <p>16)</p> <p>17)</p>	<p><i>Withania somnifera</i>; Solanaceae; Penneru, Aswagandha. (collected from Wild only} and <i>Pepper longum</i>; Piperaceae; Pippallu</p> <p>15*<i>Withania somnifera</i></p> <p><i>Pepper nigrum</i>; Piperaceae; Black pepper; Miriyalu</p>	<p>For curing T.B.</p> <p>For curing T.B.</p> <p>For curing Pneumonia</p>	<p>F13*For curing T.B., <i>Withania</i> tuber fine powder 10 gr. and dry <i>Pepper longum</i> fine powder 2 grams are mixed in together in 500 ml of water and boiled to get 250 ml of decoction, screened added with pure honey 30 gr and pure cow ghee 20 gr and given as a single dose to be consumed orally in the morning and same evening for 40 days for curing TB.</p> <p>This is followed by using the next formula as furnished below.</p> <p>F14*50 ml of decoction is prepared using 100 ml of water and 10 gr of <i>Aswagandha</i> fresh green leaves. 30 ml of Honey is added to this decoction mixed well and given to take orally in the morning and evening for 40 days for curing T.B.</p> <p>F15*For curing pneumonia, Tubers of <i>Withania</i> are burnt to ashes and @ 200 mg of the ash is mixed in 1 ml of honey given to the patient in the morning and same repeat in the evening for 40 days.</p> <p>F16*For curing Asthma <i>Withania</i> plant leaves are dried well under shade of Sun, made into a fine powder. 5 gr of this powder is mixed 5 ml of honey given to asthma patient to consume orally</p>

		For curing Asthma For curing cough	in the morning. . Like wise to be repeated thrice in a day for 21 days to 40 days F17*An incision is made in a ripe banana fruit and 1 gr of Pepper powder is inserted into it and given to consume orally once in the morning and evening for curing cough.
18)	<i>Pedaliu murex</i> ; Pedaliaceae; Enugu Palleru. and 15* <i>Withania somnifera</i> ; Solanaceae; Penneru, Aswagandha. <i>Moringa oleifera</i> ; Moringaceae;	For curing T.B.	F 18* <i>Pedaliu</i> dry fruit fine powder and <i>Aswagandha</i> fine powder are taken in equal quantities and 6 gr of this mixture is boiled in 300 ml of cow's milk and given to the patient consume orally twice in a day, in two equal split doses ie., in the morning and in the evening for 40 days. F19 * Roots bark of <i>Moringa</i> plant 20 gr is dried and powdered and 10 gr. of <i>pepper longum</i> dry fruits powder are together grinded well in a mortar with pestle. 750 mg to 1 gr of this powder is mixed in 2 ml of honey and given to the patient to consume orally in the morning and same dose in the evening. Likewise continued for few days.
19)	Drumstick; Munaga. 16* <i>Pepper longum</i> ; Piperaceae; Pippallu	For curing severe coughs of all types	
20)	<i>Acorus calamus</i> ; Acoraceae; Vasa; and 21) <i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> ; Fabaceae; Athimadhuram	For curing severe coughs of all types	F 20 * <i>Vasa</i> dried rhizome 30 gr is made in to a fine powder and Athimadhuram 30 gr is made into a fine powder. Both the powders are screened well and preserved in an air tight glass bottle. Dose @ 1 to 2 gr of powder is mixed in 2 ml of honey and given to the patient to consume orally in the morning and same dose in the evening. Likewise continued for few days.
22)	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> ; Nelumbonaceae; Lotus; Tamara	For curing severe Cough T.B. Patients	F21*A decoction is made with 1 Kg of Lotus petals are placed in a stain less steel vessel containing 2 lits of water and boiled to get a concentrate of 1 lit, screened and 250 gr of misery powder (sugar crystal lump powder) is added again heated to get a syrup. Given to the patients @ 1 ounce per time (30 ml) X 3 times a day for 10 days.
23)	<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i> ; Fabaceae; Indigo plant ; Neelimandu	For curing T.B.	F22* 10 gr of the root paste is mixed in 200 ml of cow's milk and given in the morning as a single dose and repeated the same new in the evening for 40 days
24)	<i>Derris indica</i> ; Fabaceae; Pongamea; Karanji; kaanuga	For curing whooping cough. and For all other coughs also	F23* Matured and green fruits of pongamea tree are made into a pendant or neck lace using a thread or string and worn to be around the neck of the woofing cough patient for 40 days continuously. F24* 50 ml of decoction is made using 5 to 6 <i>Pongamea</i> leaves and 1 gr of pepper powder, take orally in the morning repeat it thrice in a day for 21 days or 40 days. F25* <i>Pongamea</i> seed is grinded into a fine paste using water, and the paste is smeared on the tongue for curing whooping cough.

			F26* To brush for cleaning the teeth in the morning, <i>Pongamea</i> twig of a pencil thickness is used.
25)	13* <i>Solanumsurattense</i> ; Solanaceae; Vaakudu; Kantakari; <i>Clerodendrum serratum</i> ; Lamiaceae; Gantubaranji; 16* <i>Pepper longum</i> ; Piperaceae; Pippallu;	For curing severe cough, Asthma ; Difficulty in taking lungs in full respiration; and for TB in the initial stages;	F27* vaakudu root powder 70 gr + Gantubaranji whole plant powder 70 gr + Pippallu fruit powder 30 gr + Dried Sonti powder 70 gr are taken; mixed together and made in to a fine powder again ; screened well . This powder is preserved in a water tight glass container and used twice in a day @ 2 to 3 grams in the morning and 2 to 3 gr in the night at bed time along with honey.
26)	<i>Zingiber officinalis</i> ; Zingiberaceae; Allam; Dried Adrak; Sonti.		
27)	<i>Coldenia procumbens</i> ; Boraginaceae;Hamsapadi; Chepputattaku.	For curing Back pain	F28* Leaves juice is applied and gently massaged on the spine.
28)	<i>Commiphora mukul</i> ; Burseraceae; Guggulu, and	For curing Back pain, bone joint and Limbs: (For only external application).	F29*5 gr of white colored pure Oleo gum resin of Guggulu is taken, pounded well to make it soft. Cleaned dry date fruits 50 no's are taken. By forming a vertical cut remove the seed and the mukul gum is inserted and closed carefully by tying with a sewing thread. On each date and for all the dates, formed a coat with wet wheat powder chapathi dough, spread evenly as a thick covering (3 mm thick- uniform coat). Burnt on / in between coal cinders carefully. As soon as wheat coating becomes red, the sealed dates are removed from fire, cooled naturally and the burnt wheat coat is removed and discord. The dates are pounded to get a homogeneous powder, made in to 250 mg to 500 mg pills. Given to the patients orally, @ 1 pill in morning and 1 pill in evening along with 100 ml of cow milk for 21 day.
29)	<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i> ; Arecaceae; Khajur, Endukharjuram.		F30*250 ml of pure mustard oil is heated in a stainless steel container on a low flame, in which pounded <i>mukul</i> gum resin, 75 gr is added, Stirred well with a stainless spoon, till it dissolves in mustard oil. Applied on the painful areas, Spine, bone joints and gently massaged in the morning and evening, to get rid of pains within a week.
30)	<i>Brassica rapa</i> ; Brassicaceae; Mustard; Avalu		
	1* <i>Calotropis procera</i> ; Apocynaceae; Jilledu; 5* <i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> ; Vitaceae; Nalleru 14 * <i>Nicotina tabacum</i> ; Solanaceae.	For curing Back (spinal cord) Pain. For curing pain in knee joints FORMULA - B.	FORMULA—A. Species up to sl. no 31. F 31*Jilledu leaves pure juice (no water) 100 ml + Nalleru whole plant's pure juice 100 ml + Tobacco plant green leaves pure juice - 100 ml. + Kasivenda leaves juice 100 ml. All these 4 juices (400ml) are mixed and poured in a stainless steel vessel containing 1 lit of pure Sesame oil (With black color seeds coats) and heated on gentle fire, leaving only 1 lit of gingili oil. Oil is screened, applied and massaged gently on the painful spine, knees (body parts). Twice in a day for 10 to 15 days for excellent result.

<p>31)</p> <p>32)</p> <p>33)</p> <p>34)</p>	<p>Tobaco; Pogaku; <i>Senna occidentalis</i>; Fabaceae; Kasivenda; FORMULA – B. species from sl no 32</p> <p><i>Vitex negundo</i>; Verbinaceae; Nirgundi; Vaavili;</p> <p><i>Recinus communis</i>; Euphorbiaceae; Red castor oil plant; 4*<i>Datura stramonium</i>; Solanaceae; Nalla vummetha.</p> <p>17*<i>Pepper nigrum</i>; Piperaceae; Miriyalu</p> <p><i>Allium sativum</i>; Amaryllidaceae; Garlic: Velluli</p> <p>26* <i>Zingiber officinalis</i>; Zingiberaceae; Dried Adrak; Allam; Dried and processed zinger called Sonti.</p>	<p>For curing pain in all bone joints</p>	<p>FORMULA – B. species from Sl. No. 32</p> <p>F32* Afterwards, Pepper (black) dry seed fine powder-100 gr + Vaavili roots bark fine powder 200 gr + Red Caster dried fruits cotyledons powder 50 gr and dried roots powder of Red Caster 50 gr + Datura seeds powder 100 gr + Garlic 100 gr half pounded and Dried and processed Ginger fine powder 100 gr are added, mixed and placed in a stainless steel vessel and poured 3 liters of water mixed well. Placed on fire and boiled till we get 1 liter of concentrated decoction. Added to this decoction, 1litre of pure gingili oil. Continued heating on gentle fire till all the 1lit of decoction is evaporated leaving only 1 lit of gingili oil and allowed it to cool. Oil is screened, applied and massaged gently on the painful spine, knees (body parts). Twice in a day for 10 to 15 days for excellent results.</p>
<p>35)</p>	<p><i>Bombax ceiba</i>; Bombacaceae; Burugachettu;</p>	<p>For curing Back pain</p>	<p>F33* 200 gr of Stem bark is pounded well; Mixed with 100 ml of pure castor oil heated well in a stain less steel Kadai. Put of the flame. After the ingredients are cooled applied on the painful back evenly OR on any painful bone joints, covered with castor plant leaves and bandaged with a cloth.</p>
	<p>32*<i>Vitex negundo</i>; Verbinaceae; Nirgundi; Vaavili;</p>	<p>For curing Malarial fever</p> <p>For curing Back pain and pain in all joints</p>	<p>F34* A decoction is prepared by boiling 200 gr of garlic leaves in 500 ml of water to get 250 ml of decoction and 10 ml of decoction is mixed with 50 ml of milk and 5 gr sugar, given in the morning and evening for 1 week. 50 gr. of roots bark of Vaavili is collected dried well in shade. 2.5 gr of roots bark powder is mixed in 5ml of pure gingili oil in morning and evening for few days.</p>
		<p>For external application to overcome Back pain.</p>	<p>F35* 50 gr. of <i>Vitex</i> roots bark is collected, dried and powdered. To this 50 gr of dry ginger powder; 50 gr of Pippallu powder , 50 gr of Miriyalu powder are added. @ 5 gr. of the mixture</p>

			of the 4 ingredients is mixed in 5 to 10 ml of honey and is given in a day to be consumed orally for few days.
			F36* Seeds are dried and powdered finely and added in to 100 ml of coconut oil ; heated on fire gently and applied on the painful spine.
36)	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> ; Lamiaceae; Krishna Tulasi.	For curing Malarial Fever	F37* Roots are pounded well, placed in an earthen vessel 500 ml of water is poured and boiled to get a decoction of 250 ml. in the morning 25 ml of decoction added with 1 gr of pepper powder is given. The same is repeated in the evening and like that for 5 days.
37)	<i>Dendrocalamus sriectus</i> ; Poaceae; Sadanam or Sannaveduru.	For curing Asthma	F38*20 gr of Bamboo leaves are placed in a vessel containing 100 ml of water, 2 gr of pepper seeds are added, boiled to get 50 ml of decoc -tion. Given to take orally in two split doses per 1 day for 15 days
38)	<i>Strychnos potatorum</i> ; Loganiaceae; Chilla;	For curing Bronchitis	F39* Seeds are fried in a pan (without oil) powdered finely and made in to pills of each 2 gr each by mixing in adequate quantity of honey given @ 1 pill in the morn- ing and evening for few days.
39)	<i>Androgaphis paniculata</i> ; Acanthaceae; Nelavemu	For curing Malarial Fever	F40* 10 gr of whole pant is cleaned properly in water cut in to small pieces, soaked in 60 ml of water along with 2 gr of pounded black pepper in the evening, and in the next day in the morning the soaked water is given to the malaria effected patient to consume orally. Likewise given for 5 days.
40)	<i>Nyctanthes arbor - tristis</i> ; Oleaceae; Prijaatham;	For curing 1) Malaria and Dengue fevers; 2) Back pain 3) COUGH	F41* 10 gr of leaves mixed with 2 gr of black pepper seed. Pounded well, and the juice is prepared, screened and given to the malaria effected patient in the morning. Likewise given for 1 week
41)	<i>Albizzia lebbeck</i> ; Fabaceae; Dirisanam;	For curing Asthma and severe cough	F42* 50 gr of <i>Albizzia</i> flowers are grinded well and given to asthma patients to take orally @ 2 gr per 1 dose x 3 times a day for 7 days .
42)	<i>Alangium salvifolium</i> ; Cornaceae; Vuduga;	For curing Asthma and severe cough	F43* 10 gr of root bark is pounded well by mixing with 7 nos. Black peppers and 10 ml of water, screened in a thin cloth to get the juice and is administered orally once in a day for 7 days.
43)	<i>Leucas aspera</i> ; Lamiaceae; Drona; Tummi.	For curing Asthma and severe cough; Difficulty in breathing;	F44*2 gr of <i>Leucas aspera</i> plant flowers; + 3 gr of <i>Pergularia daemia</i> plant leaves; + 1no. of matured fruit of <i>Helicteres</i> plant are mixed together, grinded to make in to a fine paste and by mixing this paste in 25 ml of water, filtered in a thin cloth to get the juice and is given to take orally once in a day in the morning for few days.
44)	<i>Pergularia daemia</i> ; Asclepiadaceae; Dustaputeege;		
45)	<i>Helictere sisora</i> ;		

	Malvaceae; Indian screw tree; Gubatada;		
46)	<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i> ;	for curing severe cough and cough of T. B.	F 45* <i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i> tree stem bark + <i>Terminalia arjuna</i> tree stem bark + <i>Senna occidentalis</i> plant flowers are collected in equal quantities say 100 gr each; dried well, finely powdered and screened; Stored in an air tight glass bottle. 5 gr of this powder is mixed in a cup of hot milk, given to take once in a day for 40 days.
47)	Fabaceae; Yegisa; <i>Terminalia arjuna</i> ;		
48)	Combretaceae; Tellamadddi; <i>Senna occidentalis</i> ; Fabaceae; Kasinda;		
49)	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i> ; Apocynaceae; Kutaja; Kodusapala	For curing dry cough	F46* 2 gr of bark is given for chewing in the morning and in the evening for few days.
	3* <i>Strychnos nux-vomica</i> ; Loganiaceae; Musti;	Bronchitis.	F 47* <i>Nux-vomica</i> bark is rubbed with few drops of water on a grinding stone and 500 mg of this paste is given orally for smearing on tongue, once in a day for a period 10 days.

4. Conclusions

This information provides a base line data for future generations who will work on these aspects and in depth. Chemical studies would be an important aspect to find out the compounds which are responsible for curing the different ailments occurring in mankind.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors duly acknowledge the tribal people and tribal doctors in the study areas namely, Bangaruputtu, Gamparai, Laxmipeta, Peddabayalu, Munchingi puttu Villages in Munchingi puttu Mandal of Alluri Seetharama Raju District in Andhra Pradesh, for their co-operation extended during their fieldworks.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No Conflict of Interest

Statement of ethical approval

No animals were involved in this study.

References

- [1] Anonymous, WHO traditional Medicine Strategy 2002–2005. World Health Organisation, Geneva, Switzerland. (WHO/EDM/TRM/2002.1.), 2002.
- [2] P.A.Cox, M.Balick, The Ethnobotanical approach to drug discovery. *Scientific American* 270, 1994. 82–87.
- [3] S.K. Jain Directory of Ethno veterinary plants of India. Deep Publications, New Delhi.1999.
- [4] K.Hemadri, Shastra vettalanum Akashistunna Girijana Vaidyam (Tribal Pharmacopoeia). Tribal Cultural Research and Training Institute, Hyderabad.1994.
- [5] G. Martin, Ethnobotany – A method manual. Chapman and Hall, London. 1995.

- [6] NarasimhaRao, G.M. and Pragaya Murty,P. 2014 Survey and documentation of some important medicinal applications of Mangrove plants of Andhra Pradesh, India. *The Journal of Ethnobiology and Traditional Medicine*. Photon 122.842-847.
- [7] N.V. Jayanth Babu, P. Prayaga Murty and G. M. Narasimha Rao. 2017. Application of Ethno medicine to treat bone fracture in Eastern Ghats of India, AP. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences* 12(6):48-54.
- [8] N.V. Jayanth Babu, P. Prayaga Murty and G. M. Narasimha Rao. 2018. Internal application of some Ethno medicinal plants to treat bone fracture in Eastern Ghats of India, AP. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences* 13(1):34-37 DOI: 10.9790/3008-1301013437.
- [9] N.V. Jayanth Babu, P. Prayaga Murty and G. M. Narasimha Rao. 2020A. Ethnomedicinal Plants used for the Treatment of Rheumatoid Arthritis, Andhra Pradesh, India. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences (IOSR-JPBS)*, Volume 15, Issue 2 Ser. I (Mar –Apr 2020), PP 44-52.
- [10] N.V. Jayanth Babu, P. Prayaga Murty and G. M. Narasimha Rao. 2020B. Indigenous treatments and application of Ethno Medicine for treating sports injuries and other ailments. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences* 15(2 (3)):44-57.
- [11] N.V. Jayanth Babu, P. Prayaga Murty and G. M. Narasimha Rao. 2020C. Ethnomedicinal plants used to treat Osteo Arthritis from Andhra Pradesh, India. *International Journal of Botany and Research (IJBR)* Vol. 10 (1): 55-68.
- [12] N.V. Jayanth Babu, P. Prayaga Murty and G. M. Narasimha Rao. 2020D. Plant Species Utilized to Treat Skeletal Fluorosis and Fluorosis Arthritis from Eastern Ghats of Andhra Pradesh, India. *International Journal of Ayurvedic and Herbal Medicine* 10:2 (2020) 3748-3757.
- [13] N.V. Jayanth Babu, P. Prayaga Murty and G. M. Narasimha Rao. 2020E. Survey and documentation on ethnomedicinal plants used for the treatment of Osteoporosis by traditional healers in Eastern Ghats of Andhra Pradesh, India. *International Journal of Herbal Medicine*, 2020; 8(3): 25-31.
- [14] Narasimha Rao, G.M. 2020. Flora of Mangrove Species Utilized for Ethno medicinal Practices in Gautami Godavari Estuary, Andhra Pradesh, India. In book: *Medicinal Plants: Biodiversity, Sustainable Utilization and Conservation*. DOI: [10.1007/978-981-15-1636-8-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-1636-8-5).
- [15] N.V. Jayanth Babu and G.M.Narasimha Rao. 2021. Ethnomedicinal Practices of *Aeglemarmelos* in Eastern Ghats of India. In book: *The Phytochemical and Pharmacological Aspects of Ethnomedicinal Plants*. DOI:[10.1201/9781003100768-9](https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003100768-9).
- [16] N.V. Jayanth Babu, B.Raja Sekhar, K.S, Rani and Narasimha Rao G.M. 2024. External application of Ethno Veterinary plants to treat bone fractures in domestic and pet animals of the villages in Nallamalla forest region of Eastern Ghats of AP, India. *Sch. J Agric. Vet. Sci.*, 2024, 11(3):30-37.
- [17] N.V. Jayanth Babu, D.S.Madhava Rao and G.M.Narasimha Rao. 2024 A. Ethnomedicinal Plant treatment Practices in Vogue for curing different ailments in the villages of Alluru Sitarama Raju District, the Eastern Ghats of Andhra Pradesh, India. *Advances in Applied Biological Research* Vol. 1 issue 2 (July –December) DOI 10.48165/ aabr 2024.2.01.
- [18] P. Prayaga Murthy and Narasimha Rao, G.M. 2010. Unique Ethno medicinal uses of some plant species of Andhra Pradesh, India. *Journal of Phytology*, Vol: 2 (4) Pp.17-21